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(Scorpiones: Scorpionidae)**

**Kazusa Kawai, Thornthan Unnahachote,
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June 2023 — No. 373

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Publication date: 16 June 2023

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:87F75781-5547-4D0F-8DA3-8B64E41B3879>

A Review of *Heterometrus* in Thailand (Scorpiones: Scorpionidae)

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<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:pub:87F75781-5547-4D0F-8DA3-8B64E41B3879>

Summary

Five species of the genus *Heterometrus* Ehrenberg, 1828 are currently confirmed from Thailand and revised, with their respective distribution range in this country updated. *Heterometrus laevigatus* (Thorell, 1876) is considered a *nomen dubium*, while its two previous junior synonyms, *H. cimrmani* Kovařík, 2004, **stat. rev.** and *H. minotaurus* Plíšková et al., 2016, **stat. rev.** are revalidated and redescribed based on the examination of topotypes. Females of *H. minotaurus* Plíšková et al., 2016, **stat. rev.** were also collected and examined, and their characters are herein described with a special attention to sexual dimorphism. Furthermore, some populations previously regarded as *H. laoticus* Couzijn, 1981 found in Thailand turned out to belong to *H. silenus* (Simon, 1884). Additionally, ambiguous records of *H. spinifer* (Ehrenberg, 1828) in Thailand are now confirmed. Finally, we speculate that the difference in pedipalp length between males of *H. cimrmani* and *H. minotaurus* is evolved due to the arm-span competition.

Introduction

The genus *Heterometrus* Ehrenberg, 1828 belongs to subfamily Heterometrinae Simon, 1879 (family Scorpionidae Latreille, 1802) and includes medium to large-sized (total length ranges from 90 to 140 mm, with no significant interspecific difference), dark-colored scorpions, often equivocally referred to as the “Asian forest scorpions”. Dozens of species and several subgenera had been once assigned to this genus; however, Prendini & Loria (2020) elevated its four subgenera to the generic rank, and described two new genera. Currently, seven genera comprise the Heterometrinae: *Chersonesometrus* Couzijn, 1978, *Deccanometrus* Prendini & Loria, 2020, *Gigantometrus* Couzijn, 1978, *Heterometrus* Ehrenberg, 1828, *Javanimetrus* Couzijn, 1978, *Sahyadrimetrus* Prendini & Loria, 2020, and *Srilankametrus* Couzijn, 1981. Only eight species are retained in *Heterometrus*: *H. glaucus* (Thorell, 1876), *H. laevigatus* (Thorell, 1876), *H. laoticus* Couzijn, 1981, *H. longimanus* (Herbst, 1800), *H. petersii* (Thorell, 1876), *H. silenus* (Simon, 1884), *H. spinifer* (Ehrenberg, 1828), and *H. thorellii* (Pocock, 1892). Prendini & Loria (2020) considered both *H. cimrmani* Kovařík, 2004 and *H. minotaurus* Plíšková et al., 2016 as junior synonyms of *H.*

laevigatus. Most *Heterometrus* species are very difficult to be distinguished by females or juveniles, and males are important for identification (Kovařík, 2004; Prendini & Loria, 2020). However, *H. laevigatus* was described based on a single female.

In the present study, we reviewed all the species of *Heterometrus* found in Thailand. Prendini & Loria (2020: table 2) considered that only *H. laevigatus* and *H. laoticus* were found in Thailand. However, previous authors (e. g., Kovařík, 2004) have also listed Thailand as one of the countries where *H. silenus* (misidentified as *H. petersii*) and *H. spinifer* are found. The latter two species were herein thoroughly investigated, and their distribution in Thailand is now confirmed. Further, *H. cimrmani* and *H. minotaurus* are revalidated based on several morphological characters, while *H. laevigatus* is considered a *nomen dubium*. As a result, nine species now comprise the genus *Heterometrus*, of which five are recorded in Thailand.

Material, Methods and Abbreviations

Material. Specimens were collected in Thailand by the second and third authors, and several other collectors from

Figures 1–3: *Heterometrus laevigatus*, holotype subadult female (NMG 90); scale bar = 10mm. **Figure 1.** Dorsal aspect. **Figure 2.** Ventral aspect. **Figure 3.** Label.

provinces of Chanthaburi, Chonburi, Lamphun, Nakhon Si Thammarat, Narathiwat, Surat Thani, Trang and Yala; several specimens lacked specific data (e.g., date and precise location). They were examined by the first author; the fourth author only offered suggestions based on the photos. All the specimens collected and examined in this study are deposited in the Natural History Museum of Thailand (THNHM) and

in Thornthan Unnahachote's personal collection (TUPC). We also requested Naturhistoriska Riksmuseet, Göteborg, Sweden (NMG) for photographs of the holotype of *H. laevigatus*. The 12S and 16S rRNA genes were tested by the fourth author (data not provided here); COI gene analysis in progress.

Morphology. Specimens were photographed post-mortem against a white background. Males and females collected from

Dimensions (mm)		<i>H. laevigatus</i> juv. HT	<i>H. cimrmani</i> ♂ (Trang)	<i>H. cimrmani</i> ♀ (Nakhon)	<i>H. minotaurus</i> ♂ (Surat Thani)	<i>H. minotaurus</i> ♀ (Surat Thani)
Carapace	L / W	15.5 / 14.5	16.3 / 13.7	17.5 / 15.5	15.4 / 14.3	16.6 / 14.8
Mesosoma	L	31.0	25.4	27.3	23.7	31.3
Metasoma + telson	L	51.5	54.4	57.4	54.4	53.3
Segment I	L / W	5.5 / 6.5	5.4 / 7.1	5.9 / 7.2	5.7 / 7.0	5.5 / 6.9
Segment II	L / W	-	6.7 / 6.5	7.2 / 6.7	6.4 / 6.3	6.8 / 5.7
Segment III	L / W	-	7.3 / 6.0	7.9 / 6.7	7.7 / 6.7	7.3 / 5.8
Segment IV	L / W	-	8.9 / 5.4	8.6 / 5.5	8.6 / 5.3	8.7 / 5.0
Segment V	L / W	-	12.9 / 4.5	13.5 / 5.1	12.7 / 4.3	11.9 / 4.4
Telson	L	12	13.2	14.3	13.3	13.1
Pedipalp	L	52.5	65.8	56.8	66.8	57.9
Femur	L / W	13.0 / 5.8	16.3 / 6.2	13.1 / 5.8	16.9 / 6.6	13.6 / 6.0
Patella	L / W	12.0 / 5.5	17.5 / 5.9	14.4 / 5.8	17.9 / 5.9	14.6 / 6.2
Chela	L / W	27.5 / 10.3	32.0 / 10.7	29.3 / 11.5	32.0 / 9.7	29.7 / 10.0
Movable finger	L	15.6	18.3	18.5	18.7	17.7
Total	L	98	96.1	102.2	93.5	101.2

Table 1. Morphometrics (in mm) of *Heterometrus laevigatus* (holotype), *H. cimrmani* and *H. minotaurus*. Values of the type specimens are in the original descriptions.

the same locality were allowed to mate in order to collect spermatophores for investigation, which were subsequently left on the ground, retrieved, and photographed. Identification method and morphological descriptions basically follow those of Kovařík (2004), Plíšková et al (2016) and Prendini & Loria (2020). Measurements were performed by calipers to the nearest 0.1 mm. Several ratios (femur length / width (FL/W), patella length / width (PL/W), femur length / carapace length (FL/CL), chela length / width (ChL/W)) were cited from those papers if they were directly provided, and incorporated into the ratiometric ranges based on new specimens; if not, they were hereby calculated based on the raw data in those papers, to two significant figures. The morphological descriptions in this study focused only on the crucial diagnostic characters. The specimens obtained in this survey accorded with the previous morphometric range of each species.

Abbreviations. PTC, pectinal tooth count; DL, dorsolateral carinae of metasoma; DSM, dorsosubmedian carinae of metasoma; VSM, ventrosubmedian carinae of metasoma; *db*, dorsal and basal trichobothria; *dsb*, dorsal and suprabasal trichobothria; *dst*, dorsal and supraterminal trichobothria; *dt*, dorsal and terminal trichobothria; *eb*, external and basal trichobothria; *esb*, external and suprabasal trichobothria; *est*, external and supraterminal trichobothria; *et*, external and terminal trichobothria; *v*, ventral trichobothria.

Specimen depositories. FKCP (František Kovařík, private collection, Prague, Czech Republic); MNHN (Muséum National d'Histoire Naturelle, Paris, France); NMG (Naturhistoriska Riksmuseet, Göteborg, Sweden); THNH (Natural History Museum of Thailand); TUPC (Thorntan Unnahachote Personal Collection, Thailand); ZMHB (Museum für Naturkunde der Humboldt-Universität, Berlin, Germany).

Systematics

Heterometrus cimrmani Kovařík, 2004, **stat. rev.**

(Figures 4–5, 12–13, 20–21, 30–31, 40–41, 50–51, 58–59, 62–66, 82; Table 1)

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:3F0AD508-4275-459B-B3F5-47E8B67C3688>

Heterometrus spinifer spinifer: Couzijn, 1981: 89–91 (misidentification, part).

Heterometrus spinifer solitarius: Couzijn, 1981: 96 (misidentification, part).

Heterometrus cimrmani Kovařík, 2004: 1–2, 7, 9–11, 23, 42, 51, 53 (part), tables 1, 2 (part), fig. 11; 2009: 35–36, 46, 48–49, 75, 99, 102 (part), table 1 (part), figs. 14–19, 194–195, 232–237; Booncham et al., 2007: 43.

Heterometrus laevigatus: Prendini & Loria, 2020: 236–237, 240–241, 245 (part), figs. 7E, 9E, 10, 23A, B, 37A, B, 50A–D, 67D, 68D, 69D, 158, 164–168 (part), table 2 (part).

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. Thailand, *Trang Province*, Trang env. [Trang, 07.56°N 99.62°E]; FKCP.

MATERIAL EXAMINED. **Thailand**, *Nakhon Si Thammarat Province*, Thung Song District, Nam Tok [08.48°N 99.85°E], 1 November 2021, 1♀ (THNHM-Ar-00000006), leg. T. Unnahachote, TUPC; Amphoe Ronpiboon District, Tombon Ronpiboon [06.72°N 100.17°E], May 2022, 6♂6♀, TUPC; *Narathiwat Province*, Chokairong District, Bukit [06.23°N 101.86°E], 20 June 2022, 2♀ (not collected); *Trang Province*, Ratsada District, at the border with Nakhon Si Thammarat [07.95°N 99.71°E], 2021, 2♂5♀, TUPC; Nong Bua [07.97°N 99.71°E], 28 August 2021, 1♂ (THNHM-Ar-00000005), leg. A. Samutjit, TUPC.

Figures 4–11: Comparison of *Heterometrus* spp. in Thailand, metasoma and telson in dorsal aspect. **Figures 4–5.** *H. cimrmani*, male from Trang (4) and female from Nakhon Si Thammarat (5), THNHM. **Figures 6–7.** *H. minotaurus*, male (6) and female from Surat Thani (7), THNHM. **Figures 8–9.** *H. silenus*, male from Chanthaburi (8) and female from Chonburi (9), TUPC. **Figures 10–11.** *H. laoticus*, male (10) and female from Lamphun (11), TUPC.

Figures 12–19: Comparison of *Heterometrus* spp. in Thailand, metasoma and telson in ventral aspect. **Figures 12–13.** *H. cimrmani*, male from Trang (12) and female from Nakhon Si Thammarat (13), THNHM. **Figures 14–15.** *H. minotaurus*, male (14) and female from Surat Thani (15), THNHM. **Figures 16–17.** *H. silenus*, male from Chanthaburi (16) and female from Chonburi (17), TUPC. **Figures 18–19.** *H. laoticus*, male (18) and female from Lamphun (19), TUPC.

Figures 20–29: Comparison of *Heterometrus* spp. in Thailand, prosoma in dorsal aspect. **Figures 20–21.** *H. cimrmani*, male from Trang (20) and female from Nakhon Si Thammarat (21), THNHM. **Figures 22–23.** *H. minotaurus*, male (22) and female from Surat Thani (23), THNHM. **Figures 24–25.** *H. silenus*, male from Chanthaburi (24) and female from Chonburi (25), TUPC. **Figures 26–27.** *H. laoticus*, male (26) and female from Lamphun (27), TUPC. **Figures 28–29.** *H. spinifer*, males from Yala (28) and Narathiwat (29), TUPC.

DIAGNOSIS (modified from Kovařík, 2004). Total length of adults 98–115 mm (male holotype 111 mm, female allotype 98 mm). Base color of adults uniformly black, cuticular surface moderately lustrous (Figs. 62–66). Carapace with dorsal essentially smooth and laterals heavily granulated; dorsal profile triangular (resembles isosceles trapezoid) (Figs. 20–21). Tergite surface essentially smooth with few granules in both sexes (Fig. 66). PTC 14–17 in both sexes. Pedipalps relatively elongated (more slender in males, thicker and shorter in females) among congeners (Figs. 62–65); ChL/W: ♂2.8–3.0, ♀2.1–2.5; FL/W: ♂2.6–2.8, ♀2.1–2.3; PL/W: ♂2.6–3.0, ♀2.5; FL/CL: ♂0.9–1.0, ♀0.7–0.8. Dorsal surface of chelal manus moderately reticulated in both sexes, more so in females (Figs. 30–31); prodorsal surface scattered with minute spiniform granules (Figs. 50–51); fixed finger shorter than manus (Figs. 40–41). Male finger relatively curved, manus wide in vertical aspect (Fig. 50). Metasoma with VSM intercarinal distance wide; DL and DSM on metasoma I–IV curved in males; telson in adults reddish black to pitch black (Figs. 4–5, 12–13).

DISTRIBUTION. The species is distributed in southern Thailand, from the Marui River and Nakhon Si Thammarat Mountain Range to the Bang Lang and Sai Bui rivers and Sankalakhiri Mountain Range. This species has also been recorded from Langkawi Island (Malaysia).

Heterometrus minotaurus Plíšková et al., 2016,
stat. rev.

(Figures 6–7, 14–15, 22–23, 32–33, 42–43, 52–53, 60–61, 67–71; Table 1)

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:7D62EBF1-8AAD-4D32-B68D-EB6A2EB5625D>

Heterometrus spinifer spinifer: Couzijn, 1981: 89–91 (misidentification, part).

Heterometrus spinifer solitarius: Couzijn, 1981: 96 (misidentification, part).

Heterometrus minotaurus Plíšková et al., 2016: 467–474, figs. 1–23.

Heterometrus laevigatus: Prendini & Loria, 2020: 236–237, 240–241, 245 (part), figs. 7E, 9E, 10, 23A, B, 37A, B, 50A–D, 67D, 68D, 69D, 158, 164–168 (part), table 2 (part).

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. Thailand, Surat Thani Prov., Phanom District, 8°52'N 98°36'E, 395 m a. s. l.; FKCP.

MATERIAL EXAMINED. **Thailand**, *Phuket Province*, Phuket Island, 1 subadult, TUPC; *Surat Thani Province*, Chaiya District [09.44°N 99.08°E], 1♂ (THNHM-Ar-00000007) 1♀ (THNHM-Ar-00000008), 25 August 2021, leg. T. Unnahachote, Pa We [07.84°N 98.31°E], 5♂5♀, TUPC.

Figures 30–39: Comparison of *Heterometrus* spp. in Thailand, chela in dorsal aspect (trichobothria indicated by red circles). **Figures 30–31.** *H. cimmani*, male from Trang (30) and female from Nakhon Si Thammarat (31), THNHM. **Figures 32–33.** *H. minotaurus*, male (32) and female from Surat Thani (33), THNHM. **Figures 34–35.** *H. silenus*, male from Chanthaburi (34) and female from Chonburi (35), TUPC. **Figures 36–37.** *H. laoticus*, male (36) and female from Lamphun (37), TUPC. **Figures 38–39.** *H. spinifer*, males from Yala (38) and Narathiwat (39), TUPC.

DIAGNOSIS (modified from Plíšková et al., 2016). Total length of adults 83–102 mm (male holotype 83 mm). Base color of adults uniformly black, cuticular surface moderately lustrous (Figs. 67–71). Carapace with dorsal essentially smooth and laterals heavily granulated; dorsal profile triangular (resembles isosceles trapezoid) (Figs. 22–23). Tergite surface

smooth with few granules in both sexes (Fig. 67). PTC 14–18 in both sexes. Pedipalps relatively elongated (more slender in males, thicker and shorter in females) among congeners (Figs. 68–71); ChL/W: ♂3.2–3.4, ♀2.7–3.0; FL/W: ♂2.6–3.0, ♀2.3; PL/W: ♂2.9, ♀2.4; FL/CL: ♂1.0–1.1, ♀0.8. Dorsal surface of chelal manus slightly reticulated in both sexes (Figs. 32–33);

Figures 40–49: Comparison of *Heterometrus* spp. in Thailand, chela in external aspect (trichobothria indicated by red circles). **Figures 40–41.** *H. cimrmani*, male from Trang (40) and female from Nakhon Si Thammarat (41), THNHM. **Figures 42–43.** *H. minotaurus*, male (42) and female from Surat Thani (43), THNHM. **Figures 44–45.** *H. silenus*, male from Chanthaburi (44) and female from Chonburi (45), TUPC. **Figures 46–47.** *H. laoticus*, male (46) and female from Lamphun (47), TUPC. **Figures 48–49.** *H. spinifer*, males from Yala (48) and Narathiwat (49), TUPC.

prodorsal surface scattered with minute spiniform granules (Figs. 52–53); fixed finger shorter than manus (Figs. 42–43). Male finger relatively straight, manus narrow in vertical aspect (Fig. 52). Metasoma with VSM intercarinal distance wide; DL and DSM on metasoma I–IV curved in males; telson in adults reddish black to pitch black (Figs. 6–7, 14–15).

DISTRIBUTION. The species is distributed in southern Thailand, from Kra Isthmus to the Marui River and Nakhon Si Thammarat Mountain Range. This species has also been recorded from Myanmar (error).

COMMENTS.

Status of *H. laevigatus* and revalidation of *H. cimrmani* and *H. minotaurus*

Heterometrus laevigatus was originally synonymized with *H. spinifer* by Couzjin (1981: 93), followed by Kovařík (2004: 40); Kraepelin (1895: 34) listed both *H. laevigatus* and *H. spinifer* as synonyms of *H. longimanus*. This species was regarded as valid only in Keyserling (1885: 39), apart from the original description (Thorell, 1876b: 221, 222) and

Figures 50–57: Comparison of *Heterometrus* spp. in Thailand, chela in ventral aspect (trichobothria indicated by red circles). **Figures 50–51.** *H. cimirmani*, male from Trang (50) and female from Nakhon Si Thammarat (51), THNHM. **Figures 52–53.** *H. minotaurus*, male (52) and female from Surat Thani (53), THNHM. **Figures 54–55.** *H. silenus*, male from Chanthaburi (54) and female from Chonburi (55), TUPC. **Figures 56–57.** *H. laoticus*, male (56) and female from Lamphun (57), TUPC.

Figures 58–61: *Heterometrus* spp., post-mating spermatophores in bilateral aspects. **Figures 58–59.** *H. cimrmani* from Trang. **Figures 60–61.** *H. minotaurus* from Surat Thani.

Prendini & Loria (2020). However, apart from the differences (reticulations on pedipalp manus, sum length of metasoma I–IV, and trichobothrial distances between *V* series on chela) already noted by Couzjin (1981), the prodorsal surface of the chela differs considerably from that of *H. spinifer*: pronounced spiniform granules are present in *H. spinifer* (Figs. 38–39), but they are weaker in *H. laevigatus* (Figs. 1–2). Therefore, it is not credible to synonymize *H. laevigatus* with *H. spinifer*.

The holotype (and the only type specimen) of *H. laevigatus* is a subadult female labeled as collected from “Nova Hollandia [Australia], Melbourne” in 1860 (Fig. 3) and was examined by Prendini & Loria (2020: 237) who considered it conspecific with *H. cimrmani*, as well as with *H. minotaurus* (Prendini & Loria, 2020: 240–241). However, they also argued that “...As in other scorpionid taxa, adult males are important for species identification and delimitation in Asian forest scorpions, and there are several species complexes comprising morphologically similar, range-restricted or narrowly endemic species (Prendini, 2001a)...Without series, especially adult males, the diagnostic characters (coloration, granulation, meristic variation) often presented to justify putative new species are unreliable and comparisons made with other species, the adults of which may or may not have

been described, invalid...” (Prendini & Loria, 2020: 12). The information of the holotype is not sufficient enough to justify their synonymization as it was a single subadult female with erroneous locality. However, the possibility that *H. laevigatus* is either *H. cimrmani* or *H. minotaurus* cannot be discarded. Comparison between subadult females could be biased; thus, *H. laevigatus* is hereby considered as a *nomen dubium* due to the ambiguity of its authentic type locality and the lack of description for adults of both sexes.

Validity of both *H. cimrmani* and *H. minotaurus* is confirmed also by DNA analysis implemented by Charles University in Prague (paper in preparation; F. Kovařík, pers. comm.).

Distribution of *H. cimrmani* and *H. minotaurus* in Thailand

H. cimrmani was described by Kovařík (2004) with the type locality from Trang Province, while *H. minotaurus* was based on a single adult male collected from Surat Thani Province (Plíšková et al., 2016). Prendini & Loria (2020: 240, 245) reported “*H. laevigatus*” from the provinces of Bangkok, Chumphon, Kanchanaburi, Krabi, Nakhon Si Thammarat, Narathiwat, Pattani, Phang Nga, Phattalung, Phetchaburi,

Satun, Songkhla, Surat Thani, and Trang, including the islands of Ko Lanta, Ko Muk, Ko Samui, the Phi Phi archipelago, and Phuket. Beyond Thailand, it was also recorded from Langkawi Island in the state of Kedah, Malaysia. According to their figure 158 (Prendini & Loria, 2020: 277), this species also occurs in Prachuap Khiri Khan and two localities in Myanmar, west to Kanchanaburi and Prachuap Khiri Khan in Thailand. Those records were not further elucidated.

The type locality of *H. minotaurus*, Surat Thani, is adjacent to Nakhon Si Thammarat where *H. cimrmani* occurs (locality of paratypes; Kovařík, 2004: 9). However, specimens of *H. minotaurus* were collected from the western region of Surat Thani, not very close to Nakhon Si Thammarat which borders it in the south. The two provinces are also separated by the Marui River on the west and the Nakhon Si Thammarat Range on the east. Based on this geographical pattern interpreted from the original information on both species, the records of “*H. laevigatus*” from Bangkok, Chumphon, Kanchanaburi, Phang Nga, Phetchaburi, Phuket, Prachuap Khiri Khan and Surat Thani are hereby assumed to be those of *H. minotaurus*. There are no clear boundaries such as mountain ranges or large rivers between the distribution range of *H. laoticus* and that of *H. minotaurus*. According to Prendini & Loria (2020: 247), the two species overlap in the provinces of Bangkok and Kanchanaburi. *H. laoticus* also occurs in Ratchaburi (Prendini & Loria, 2020: 252), which is also within the distributional range of *H. minotaurus*, although so far there is no record of the latter species therein. The alleged records from Myanmar are also regarded as the distribution of this species beyond Thailand considering the geography. All the remaining records are hence presumed to be those of *H. cimrmani* which thus is sympatrically with *H. spinifer* in Narathiwat. The single paratype female of *H. cimrmani* from Saigon (Hoshimin), Vietnam (Kovařík, 2004), was either mislabeled or misidentified (Prendini & Loria, 2020).

Morphological differences between *H. cimrmani* and *H. minotaurus*

Despite being highly resemblant with each other, the two species can be distinguished by the following characters (*H. cimrmani* vs. *H. minotaurus*): (1) total length: greatly overlapped (98–115 mm vs. 83–102 mm), however, more *H. cimrmani* individuals tend to exceed 100 mm while most *H. minotaurus* are below thereof; (2) ChW/L: both sexes of *H. minotaurus* exhibit more elongated pedipalp chela than their corresponding sexes of *H. cimrmani*, female *H. cimrmani* (2.1–2.5) < female *H. minotaurus* (2.7–3.0) < male *H. cimrmani* (2.8–3.0) < male *H. minotaurus* (3.2–3.4); (3) FL/CL: male *H. minotaurus* tends to have more elongated femur, female *H. cimrmani* (0.74–1.0) < female *H. minotaurus* (0.8) < male *H. cimrmani* (0.9–1.0) < male *H. minotaurus* (1.0–1.1); (4) surface morphosculture of chela in females: more reticulated vs. more levigated (Figs. 31, 33, 41, 43); (5) spiniform granules on prodorsal surface of chela: smaller vs. larger (Figs. 35–38, 50–53); (6) texture of chela and tergite: matte vs. lustrous (Figs. 35–38, 40–43, 50–53, 62–71); (7) pedipalp finger curvity of males: curved vs. more linear (Figs. 30, 32, 50, 52); (8) shape of metasoma I–III in males:

rounded vs. nearly straight (Figs. 4, 6), caused by the curvity of metasomal carinae (DL and DSM); (9) intercarinal distance between VSM: generally wider vs. narrower (Figs. 12–15); (10) dentation on DL: smooth vs. serrated (Figs. 4–7). There is an obvious morphological character gradient between the two species. Four characters are very subtle with minor differences (characters 1, 4, 5, and 6); values of ratiometrics are tightly adjacent (characters 2 and 3). The four qualitative characters may be informative to some degree (characters 7–10), but the differences discovered could be affected by a low sample size which can eclipse the utility of those characters in practice. Overall, the two species are mainly distinguished by the shape of chela in males, which is more elongated and flattened with straighter fingers in *H. minotaurus*, along with the different metasomal carinal curvity and distance. Conclusively, the two species can be separated by a combination of characters, but this is highly reliant on male specimens. Additional comparative figures are uploaded on ResearchGate to support our findings.

Based on the above morphological differences and the distribution patterns, *H. cimrmani* and *H. minotaurus* are hereby considered as different species. With regard to the trichobothriotaxy of male chela, Et_4 appears to be more deviated from the anteroinferior margin of manus below the base of the fixed finger in *H. cimrmani* than *H. minotaurus* (Figs. 40, 42). However, as described below, this difference is observed even among individuals that are assumed to be *H. spinifer*. As a result, the trichobothriotaxy may not be applicable for the identification of *Heterometrus* species.

Heterometrus spinifer (Ehrenberg, 1828)

(Figures 28–29, 38–39, 48–49, 80–81, 83)

<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:55E9068D-F3B9-444B-A77A-6062BC06407A>

Buthus (Heterometrus) spinifer Ehrenberg in Hemprich & Ehrenberg, 1828: pl. 1, fig. 2.

Heterometrus spinifer: Kovařík, 2004: 40–42.

Heterometrus spinifer (in part): Prendini & Loria, 2020: 290–302, figs. 10, 23, 50, 67–69, 157, 184–188 (reference list until 2020).

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. India (incorrect); ZMHB.

MATERIAL EXAMINED. **Thailand**, *Narathiwat Province*, Sungai Kolok District, Su-ngai Kolok Town [06.03°N 101.97°E], 1♂, 11 June 2021, leg. Azizi Mayi, TUPC; *Yala Province*, Be Tong District, Tano Maero [05.87°N 101.11°E], 1♂, 28 June 2021, leg. K. Saechan, TUPC, 1♀, 20 September 2022, leg. P. Pawangkhanant, TUPC.

DIAGNOSIS (modified from Kovařík, 2004 and Prendini & Loria, 2020). Total length of adults 100–135 mm. Base color of adults uniformly black, cuticular surface highly lustrous. Carapace with dorsal essentially smooth but laterals granulated; dorsal profile rectangular (Figs. 28–29). Tergites smooth with few granules and highly lustrous (Figs. 80–81). PTC 15–19 in both sexes. Pedipalps relatively elongated in

Figures 62–65: *Heterometrus cimrmani*, in dorsal (62, 64) and ventral (63, 65) aspects; scale bar = 10 mm. **Figures 62–63.** Male from Trang, THNHM. **Figures 64–65.** Female from Nakhon Si Thammarat, THNHM.

both sexes (similar in both sexes; cf. Prendini & Loria: figs. 184–185) among congeners, resembling that of female *H. longimanus*, differed from which with a more pronounced proximal lobe on cutting edge of pedipalp movable finger (cf. Prendini & Loria: figs. 177, 187); chelae of both sexes robust and moderately elongated, ChL/W: ♂♀2.4–2.6; FL/CL: ♂♀ < 0.74. Dorsal surface of chelal manus smooth in both sexes; prodorsal surface scattered with prominently large and acute spiniform granules (Figs. 38–39); fixed finger shorter than manus (Figs. 48–49). Proximal lobe on cutting edge of movable finger lacks pronounced sexual dimorphism, moderately developed in both sexes (cf. Prendini & Loria: fig. 187). Telson in adults orangish red to blackish red (Figs. 80–81), become pitch black in elder individuals.

VARIATIONS. The internal spiniform granules of chela manus vary in size. The specimen collected from Yala Province has larger granules (Fig. 38) than the one collected from Narathiwat Province (Fig. 39); the latter also has a more elongated and flattened chela. An intraspecific variation was also observed in the relative position of trichobothrium Et_4 . The specimen from Yala has the Et_4 closer to the anteroinferior margin of manus below the base of the fixed finger (Fig. 48), while it is deviated therefrom in the specimen from Narathiwat (Fig. 49).

DISTRIBUTION. This species is distributed in Thailand in the southern part near the border with Malaysia. This species also is widely distributed in the peninsular Malaysia and Tioman Island (Prendini & Loria, 2020: 295).

COMMENTS.

Distribution of *Heterometrus spinifer*

This species was described by Ehrenberg in 1828 as *Buthus spinifer*, based on a specimen supposedly from India. “India” was considered an erroneous type locality by Kovařík (2004: 40, 42). Couzijn (1981: 91) did not find the holotype and presumed that it was destroyed during World War II, but he found an older mature male specimen, which resembled the illustration and description of the holotype, collected in “India” and labeled “B.” for *Buthus*. However, this specimen had several differences from the original illustration, and Couzijn (1981) was not convinced that this specimen was the holotype. On the contrary, he designated a neotype collected in Kedah, Malaysia. Kovařík (2004) examined the male specimen from “India” and concluded that it was the holotype, which thus invalidated the neotype. The type locality of this species is thus not clarified; however, *H. spinifer* is abundant in Malaysia (Prendini & Loria, 2020: 295, 298–299, 302).

Kovařík (2004: 40) reported *H. spinifer* from Thailand with records in Bangkok, Be Tong and Phang Nga. However, Kovařík (2004) also assumed the record in Bangkok was erroneous. The only species recognized by Prendini & Loria (2020: 240–241) from Phang Nga was “*H. laevigatus*” (now *H. minotaurus*). They did not re-investigate the population in Be Tong. Interestingly, in their examined material list,

Prendini & Loria (2020: 298) reported a male from “Thailand, Burma, Southeast Asia” collected in 1949, but they did not further discuss this record. We obtained specimens from in southern Be Tong (Yala Province) and confirmed them to be conspecific with *H. spinifer*, supporting this record mentioned by Kovařík (2004). Moreover, *H. spinifer* and *H. cimrmani* (ex. “*H. laevigatus*”) were also collected from Narathiwat Province in our survey, indicating a sympatric distribution therein without clear boundaries.

The pedipalp chelae of the specimens collected from both provinces (Narathiwat and Yala, located in the south of Thailand) tend to be thinner than those of the specimens collected from Malaysia. The several characteristics in pedipalps are different between the specimens collected from the two provinces which are separated by the Sankalakhiri Mountain Range (west of Narathiwat and east of Yala), but both near the border with Malaysia. Couzijn (1981: 91) also reported this species from Thailand in the following areas: Ban Laem (“Ban Lem Ngob”), Bangkok, Bang Saphan (misspelled as “Bangtaphan”) and Koh Chang. A subspecies, *H. spinifer solitarius* (= *H. spinifer*), was also asserted to be rare in Thailand (Couzijn, 1981: 96). Based on the current knowledge, we believe those to be the records of *H. cimrmani* and *H. minotaurus*.

Morphological comparison of *Heterometrus spinifer* with its congeners

H. spinifer is most similar to *H. cimrmani* and *H. minotaurus* among the species occurring in Thailand, sharing a lustrous cuticle and relatively elongated pedipalps. However, several characters can be applied to distinguish it from the latter two: (1) telson coloration: color changes from juveniles to elder adults in *H. spinifer* (white → whitish yellow → yellow → orange → orangish red → red → blackish red → black), but constantly brownish black to reddish black (or pitch black in elder individuals) in the other two species; (2) pedipalp sexual dimorphism and ratio: weak sexual dimorphism with less elongated pedipalps of ChL/W = 2.4–2.6 in both sexes in *H. spinifer*, but ♂2.6–2.8 ♀2.1–2.3 in *H. cimrmani* and ♂3.2–3.4 ♀2.7–3.0 in *H. minotaurus*; (3) body size: often larger in *H. spinifer*; (4) chelal finger: proportionally longer when comparing with *H. cimrmani* (but similar with males of *H. minotaurus*); (5) cuticle surface: more lustrous in *H. spinifer*.

Beyond Thailand, *H. petersii* (Thorell, 1876) is the most resemblant species with *H. spinifer* among all *Heterometrus* species in all aspects, and a cryptic species to *H. spinifer* that can only be distinguished by DNA (Prendini & Loria, 2020: 278, 295, 298). Nevertheless, the possibility of *H. petersii* being the actual species of the two populations must be eliminated. Prendini & Loria (2020: 272–273) stated that there are “...no consistent morphological differences between *H. petersii* and *H. spinifer*...”. However, pronounced spiniform granules on the prodorsal surface of the chela were visible in the photos of *H. spinifer* provided by Prendini & Loria (2020: figs. 187–188), while the female holotype of *H.*

Figures 66–67: Courtship in *Heterometrus* spp., between males (left) and females (right). **Figure 66.** *H. cimrmani* from Trang. **Figure 67.** *H. minotaurus* from Surat Thani.

petersii showed a lack thereof (Prendini & Loria, 2020: fig. 178). In the photograph of a male *H. petersii* used by Loria & Prendini (2020: fig. 1F), the spiniform granules were also less prominent than those of *H. spinifer*. We checked the original photograph series to which that photo belongs (iNaturalist, obs. ID = 13070334) and confirmed that the granules are very blunt and interfused compared with those of *H. spinifer* which are often expressed as explicit rows of sharp granules. Several other photos of presumably *H. petersii* from Singapore also revealed similar random configurations (iNaturalist, obs. ID = 32882891, 140218281, 145966755 and 148539827). Based on this character, the two specimens found in this survey were identified as *H. spinifer* for their pronounced spiniform granules, as well as the geography. However, this character can be intraspecifically variable between sexes and among populations and may not be reliable for diagnosis (pers. comm. of V. Tang to S. Loria). As above noted, the size of the spiniform granules of *H. spinifer* from Narathiwat and from Yala is slightly different.

***Heterometrus laoticus* Couzijn, 1981**

(Figures 10–11, 18–19, 26–27, 36–37, 46–47, 56–57, 72–75)
<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:36ECBCC-A638-4D5E-AA78-6B9AAC2F626F>

Heterometrus laoticus Couzijn, 1981: 94 (part); Prendini & Loria, 2020: 245–252, figs. 7F, 8F, 10, 24A, B, 38A, B, 51A–D, 70A, 71A, 72A, 157, 169–173, table 2 (reference list until 2020).

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. Laos, Neis; MNHN RS 0030.

MATERIAL EXAMINED. **Thailand**, *Lamphun Province*, Mae Tha District, May 2019, 1♂1♀, TUPC.

DIAGNOSIS (modified from Kovařík, 2004 and Prendini & Loria, 2020). Total length of adults 90–125 mm (male holotype 117 mm; Couzijn, 1981). Base color of adults uniformly black, cuticular surface weakly to moderately lustrous (Figs. 72–75). Carapace surface essentially smooth, with few granules scattered on lateral surfaces but absent in anteromedian area; dorsal profile triangular (resembles isosceles trapezoid) (Figs. 26–27). Tergite surface in both sexes smooth with few granules (Figs. 72–75). PTC 15–19 in both sexes. Pedipalp relatively stout and short in both sexes among congeners (Figs. 72–75); chelae of both sexes robust and short, ChL/W: ♂♀ 2.0–2.3; FL/CL: ♂♀ < 0.74. Dorsal surface of chelal manus smooth in both sexes (Figs. 36–37); prodorsal surface scattered with minute spiniform granules (Figs. 56–57); fixed finger shorter than manus (Figs. 46–47). Proximal lobe on cutting edge of movable finger lacks pronounced sexual dimorphism, but that of the males is slightly larger than females (Figs. 46–47). Telson in adults reddish black to pitch black (Figs. 10–11, 18–19).

DISTRIBUTION. This species is widely distributed in northern, central, and western Thailand. This species is found in Laos; the record from Cambodia is doubtful (see below).

***Heterometrus silenus* (Simon, 1884)**

(Figures 8–9, 16–17, 24–25, 34–35, 44–45, 54–55, 76–79)
<http://zoobank.org/urn:lsid:zoobank.org:act:E6CFAE8B-9696-4A57-B97B-8790C8563C4D>

Palamnaeus silenus Simon, 1884: 361.

Heterometrus petersii: Kovařík, 2004: 32, 34 (misidentification, part).

Heterometrus silenus (part): Prendini & Loria, 2020: 279–290, figs. 10, 24C, D, 51E–H, 70C, 72C, 158, 179–183, table 2 (reference list until 2020).

TYPE LOCALITY AND TYPE DEPOSITORY. Philippines, Mindanao (incorrect); MNHN RS 0023.

MATERIAL EXAMINED. **Thailand**, *Chanthaburi Province*, Pluang City, 12°49'N 102°07'E, found dead on the street, 1♂, TUPC; *Khao Khitchakut District*: 12°82'N 102°13'E, 1♂, TUPC; *Chonburi Province*, Si Racha District, Bang Phra, 13°11'N 101°03'E, 1♀, TUPC; *Maharakham Province*, 16.23°N 103.23°E, 1♂, TUPC.

DIAGNOSIS (modified from Kovařík, 2004 (as *H. petersii*) and Prendini & Loria, 2020). Total length of adults 90–125 mm. Base color of adults uniformly black, cuticular surface weakly lustrous (Figs. 76–79). Carapace surface relatively granular, with obvious granules presented in anteromedian area; dorsal profile rectangular (Figs. 24–25). Tergite lateral surfaces with numerous granules and appear rough (Figs. 76–79). PTC 15–19 in both sexes. Pedipalp relatively stout and short in both sexes among congeners (Figs. 76–79); chelae of both sexes robust and short, ChL/W: ♂♀ 2.0–2.3; FL/CL: ♂♀ < 0.74. Dorsal surface of chelal manus smooth in both sexes (Figs. 34–35); prodorsal surface scattered with minute spiniform granules (Figs. 54–55); fixed finger shorter than manus (Figs. 44–45). Proximal lobe on cutting edge of movable finger exhibits pronounced sexual dimorphism, being conspicuously stronger in males than in females (Figs. 44–45). Telson in adults reddish black to pitch black (Figs. 8–9, 16–17).

DISTRIBUTION. This species is distributed in the eastern part of Thailand. This species also is found in Cambodia and Vietnam.

COMMENTS.

Distribution of *H. laoticus* and *H. silenus* in Thailand

Kovařík (2004: 32, 34) listed Bangkok and Prachinburi as the distribution areas of *H. silenus* in Thailand (misidentified as *H. petersii*), considering them doubtful (as *H. laoticus*). Prendini & Loria (2020: 247, 251–252) considered only *H. laoticus* occurs in those areas and further reported it from the provinces of Chanthaburi, Chiang Mai, Chonburi, Kamphaeng Phet, Kanchanaburi, Lampang, Lamphun, Loei, Lop Buri, Nakhon Phathom, Nakhon Ratchasima, Nakhon Sawan, Nan, Phetchabun, Phrae, Sakon Nakhon, Tak, Trat, Ubon Ratchathani and Udon Thani in Thailand.

In this survey, specimens were collected from Chanthaburi and Chonburi, and confirmed to be *H. silenus*. Geographically,

Figures 68–71: *Heterometrus minotaurus*, in dorsal (68, 70) and ventral (69, 71) aspects; scale bar = 10 mm. **Figures 68–69.** Male from Surat Thani, THNHM. **Figures 70–71.** Female from Surat Thani, THNHM.

Figures 72–75: *Heterometrus laoticus*, in dorsal (72, 74) and ventral (73, 75) aspects; scale bar = 10 mm. Figures 72–73. Male from Lamphun, TUPC. Figures 74–75. Female from Lamphun, TUPC.

Figures 76–79: *Heterometrus silenus*, in dorsal (76, 78) and ventral (77, 79) aspects; scale bar = 10 mm. **Figures 76–77.** Male from Chanthaburi, TUPC. **Figures 78–79.** Female from Chonburi, TUPC.

Figures 80–81: *Heterometrus spinifer*, in vivo habitus and dorsal aspect. **Figure 80.** Male from Yala, TUPC. **Figure 81.** Male from Narathiwat, TUPC.

Figure 82: Arm-span competition between males of *Heterometrus cimrmani* from Phattalung.

the population in Trat is also likely to be conspecific. Hence, of the provinces which were considered as the localities of *H. laoticus* listed by Prendini & Loria (2020), these three provinces are probably the records of *H. silenus* in reality; therefore, we removed those provinces from the distribution of *H. laoticus* in our study. In fact, Prendini & Loria (2020: 251–252) did not verify the specimens collected from these areas according to their material list, although they included them as the distribution areas for *H. laoticus* in the previous text (Prendini & Loria, 2020: 247). Also, they corrected a few regions plotted in figure 158 that were not mentioned in the text. *H. silenus* was also collected from Nakhon Pathom and Nakhon Ratchasima in this study, which shows a sympatric distribution with *H. laoticus* in those two provinces without clear boundaries. Two provinces, Ratchaburi and Sakon Nakhon, inferred from iNaturalist were further confirmed by the second author (no specimen collected).

Prendini & Loria (2020: 247) listed Laos and Cambodia as the two additional countries where *H. laoticus* occurs besides Thailand. Whereas Laos is the type locality of this species that lies in the north of Thailand, the record from northwestern Cambodia (Siem Reap Province; Prendini &

Loria, 2020: 251) is most likely to be *H. silenus*. As stated in Prendini & Loria (2020: 286), *H. silenus* is endemic to western Cambodia, bordering the eastern Thailand. The records of *H. laoticus* from the east of Thailand are, as confirmed in this study, in fact *H. silenus*. Prendini & Loria (2020: 248, 286) argued that the Mekong River (in Laos and Cambodia) and Annamite Mountains (in Laos) are the geographic barriers that delimit the distribution of *H. silenus* (Mekong River is west to Annamite Mountains). *H. silenus* was considered to be distributed to the east of Annamite Mountains (Prendini & Loria, 2020: 248) and blocked by the Mekong River in the west (Prendini & Loria, 2020: 286). This is geographically confusing as the western delimitation by Mekong River does not necessarily prevent *H. silenus* occurring in the west of Annamite Mountains. As they also stated (Prendini & Loria, 2020: 286), although *H. laoticus* distribute to the west of the Annamite Mountains, individuals of *H. silenus* were also collected on the west side of Mekong River (therefore, it also is found on the western side of the Annamite Mountains). We believe that *H. laoticus* does not occur in Cambodia and the records from Cambodia and southern Thailand are all *H. silenus*.

Figures 83: Arm-span competition between males of *Heterometrus spinifer* from Yala (right) and Narathiwat (left).

Morphological comparison of *H. laoticus* and *H. silenus*

H. laoticus and *H. silenus* are two highly resemblant sister species, but they can be distinguished by the following characters (*H. laoticus* vs. *H. silenus*): (1) granulation of carapace: essentially smooth with scarce granules vs. conspicuously granular (especially on the lateral surfaces) (Figs. 24–27); (2) granulation of tergites: smooth and lustrous (Figs. 72–75) vs. granular and matte (Figs. 76–79); (3) proximal lobe on the cutting edge of pedipalp movable finger: weakly sexual dimorphic vs. strongly sexual dimorphic (more developed in males and stronger than males of *H. laoticus*) (Figs. 44–47); (4) dorsal profile of carapace: triangular vs. rectangular (Figs. 24–27). Upon examining the relative position of trichobothria on the chela, it was found that the Et_1 – Est interval was wider in *H. laoticus* than in *H. silenus* (Figs. 54–57), although trichobothrial patterns can vary slightly among individuals and regional populations. However, this rule held true for

all individuals examined in this study; hence, this method is assumed to be effective for discriminating the two species. Several continuous and discrete morphometrics overlap between the two species (*H. laoticus* vs. *H. silenus*): (1) total length: both 90–125 mm; (2) PTC: both 15–19 in sexes; (3) FL/CL: both < 0.74; (4) ChL/W: 2.0–2.3 vs. 2.0–2.4.

The key characters are the differences in carapace granulation and finger lobe (Kovařík, 2004: 21, as *H. petersii*; Prendini & Loria, 2020: 246, 283, 286). The adult male specimen collected from Chanthaburi in this survey showed granular carapace (Fig. 24) and tergites, and pronounced finger lobes (Fig. 44, 77), consistent with the characters of *H. silenus* and thus confirming the occurrence of this species in Thailand. The female from Chonburi also exhibited numerous granules on its carapace (Fig. 25) and tergites, confirming the occurrence of *H. silenus* in another province of Thailand. On the other hand, a pair of specimens collected from Lamphun were smooth on carapace (Figs. 26–27) and tergites, and therefore concluded as *H. laoticus*.

Figure 84: Map showing confirmed distribution of five *Heterometrus* species in Thailand. For *H. laoticus*, previously published data are partly accepted.

Discussion

Our survey confirmed five species of *Heterometrus* from Thailand, namely *H. cimrmani*, *H. laoticus*, *H. minotaurus*, *H. silenus* and *H. spinifer*. These species can be roughly categorized into two groups: (1) tegument lustrous, with relatively elongated pedipalps (*H. cimrmani*, *H. minotaurus* and *H. spinifer*); (2) tegument matte, with short and robust pedipalps (*H. laoticus* and *H. silenus*). As shown in the map (Fig. 84), Group 1 covers the north of Thailand and Group 2 covers the south thereof. *H. laoticus* and *H. silenus* are separated by the Bang Pa Kong River and Phanom Dongrak

Mountain Range, whereas *H. cimrmani* and *H. minotaurus* are separated by the Marui River and Nakhon Si Thammarat Mountain Range. *H. cimrmani* is further isolated from *H. spinifer* by the Bang Lang and Sai Bui rivers and Sankalakhiri Mountain Range.

In the phylogenetic tree proposed by Prendini & Loria (2020: 26, fig. 10), *H. laoticus* and *H. silenus* were recovered to form a sister clade, and so were “*H. laevigatus*” and *H. spinifer*. The clade that comprised *H. laoticus* and *H. silenus* was separated from that of “*H. laevigatus*” and *H. spinifer* by a synapomorphy in the ventrosubmedian and ventrolateral carinae of metasomal segments I–IV (character 173). It is

obvious that *H. laoticus* and *H. silenus* are sister species in terms of their external morphological characters, as well as the geographical proximity that is also demonstrated in this survey. Since the former junior synonyms of *H. laevigatus* are now revalidated, we reconsidered the (*H. laevigatus*, *H. spinifer*) clade as ((*H. cimrmani*, *H. minotaurus*), (*H. spinifer*)).

The two species that comprise Group 1 defined here are obligatory burrowers, indicating a relatively low dispersal ability. Although *Heterometrus* species have not been reported to dig burrows with their pedipalps, the relatively short and stout pedipalps may not be suitable for a long-distance locomotion, nor will it ideally serve the function of a wide-range environmental detection and navigation. On the other hand, the three species in Group 2 possess a pair of relatively long pedipalps and elongated legs, suggesting that they are more likely to travel beyond their burrows. As mentioned by Prendini & Loria (2020: 36), some species with larger median ocelli and elongated legs are corticolous (e. g., *H. longimanus* (Herbst, 1800), also *H. spinifer*, with multiple observations on the tree trunks (e. g., iNaturalist, obs. ID = 161263503, 146026404, 137500214, 137366242, 137118730, 124368569, 107600946, 65612040, 61305899, 53098749, 41284259, 31582883, 32934930). The tree-climbing behavior is also observed in *H. cimrmani* (iNaturalist, obs. ID = 18446494).

Another ecological role regarding the pedipalp ratio lies in the intraspecific competition. Both *H. laoticus* and *H. silenus* will fight violently in captivity when they meet a conspecific competitor, wielding their muscular chelae to crush the body of an opponent, or simply showing their strength by thumping the opponent (Tang, 2023: 13). However, in the species where the males have relatively long pedipalps of Group 2, i.e., *H. cimrmani* and *H. minotaurus*, they resort to a completely different method (Fig. 31). The males will spread their pedipalps laterally as if they are opening their arms. Then, they approach and collide each other to demonstrate their strength. They may pinch each other but not as violent as in the first group. This behavior was defined as the arm-span competition (Tang, 2023) and has also observed in other congeners which males have elongated pedipalps (e.g., *H. longimanus* and *H. thorellii* (Pocock, 1892)). Interestingly, although no sexual dimorphism is present in *H. spinifer*, this species also employs this relatively gentle and ritualized way of competition (Fig. 32). It is also worth noting that Tang (2023: 11) "...*Arm-span competition is so far only observed in Heterometrinae...*", but this behavior has been subsequently confirmed in at least one Opisthophthalminae species, *Opisthophthalmus carinatus* (Peters, 1861), indicating that the elongated chelae in some male *Opisthophthalmus* species may also serve the same function.

The general trend of ecological adaptations of the two groups accords well with the hypothesized phylogeny. However, it remains uncertain as for the ecological function of the color change in telson (black to red, from north to south) and the texture change in tegument (matte to lustrous, from north to south). Probably, the red telson in *H. spinifer* may be used to attract the attention of the predator. This could be supported by a higher rate of encountering predators which is

likely as this species tends to be more vagrant. We assume that the more lustrous tegument may serve as a camouflage in the wet rainforest with ubiquitous reflections of water when the scorpions are outside their shelters, while for those remain in their burrow this is not needed.

Loria & Prendini (2020) reconstructed the diversification of Heterometrinae based on the "Out of India" hypothesis. The Heterometrinae taxa were hypothesized to be carried by India from Gondwana to Eurasia, separated from their sister taxon, Pandininae, in the Cretaceous. During the Tertiary dispersal, ancestors of *Heterometrus* on the Indian landmass dispersed south to Indochina and the Malay Peninsula, and north to the Philippines (Loria & Prendini, 2020: 4, fig. 2). According to the distributional pattern surveyed in this study, it seems that the *Heterometrus* species in Thailand may have altered their morphological characters as they were dispersing into Malaysia (Group 1 to Group 2). Presumably, *H. spinifer* is the most derived species in the clade ((*H. laoticus*, *H. silenus*), ((*H. cimrmani*, *H. minotaurus*), (*H. spinifer*))). Thick, tall trees are more abundant in Malaysia (lowland dipterocarp composes the majority of Malaysia vegetation; Saw, 2010: 24, table 3), which may provide suitable refuges for species like *H. spinifer* to wander around, while the Group 1 species are more conservative (similar to their relatives in Pandininae) and choose to stay in burrows. Similar vegetation also presents in the southern part of Thailand (Laongpol et al., 2009). The more intense monsoon that causes floods in southern Thailand and northern Malaysia may be another environmental factor that forces scorpions to leave their shelters and may even drive them to climb trees. Annual rainfall is relatively lower in the regions where *H. laoticus* and *H. silenus* occur (Maxwell, 2004: 20, fig. 1). Generally, in the far south (Ranong Province) and southeast, the annual rainfall is about 3000–4500 mm and the dry period lasts 3–8 weeks, while the rainfall decreases (1000–2000 mm/year) and dry period increases (3–5 months) towards the north and northeast (Maxwell, 2004). The longer dry period may have forced the scorpions to stay in their burrows which are more humid and cooler, rendering them to be specialized in burrowing. On the contrary, the arm-span competition exhibited in Group 2 may contribute to the reduction of the mortality from intraspecific collision as they may already suffer from natural disasters; however, species in both groups are also observed to be tolerant beneath water for a certain period (Tang, pers. obs.).

Dichotomous key to *Heterometrus* in Thailand

1. Male ChL/W ≤ 2.3 ; cuticle weakly to moderately lustrous. 2
 - Male ChL/W ≥ 2.4 ; cuticle moderately to highly lustrous. 3
2. Proximal lobe on cutting edge of pedipalp movable finger not prominently sexually dimorphic; carapace essentially smooth, with scarce granules on lateral surfaces... *H. laoticus*
 - Proximal lobe on cutting edge of pedipalp movable finger prominently sexually dimorphic with that in males pronounced; carapace granular, with granules evenly scattered. . *H. silenus*

3. Male ChL/W ≥ 2.8 ; prodorsal surface of chela with small to moderate spiniform granules. 4
– Male ChL/W ≤ 2.6 ; prodorsal surface of chela with pronounced spiniform granules. *H. spinifer*
4. Male ChL/W ≤ 3.0 ; DSM of male curved.
..... *H. cimrmani* **stat. rev.**
– Male ChL/W ≥ 3.1 ; DSM of male straight.
..... *H. minotaurus* **stat. rev.**

Acknowledgments

We thank Charlotte Jonsson for sending photographs of the holotype of *H. laevigatus*, and two anonymous reviewers and František Kovařík for their comments.

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Appendix

Updated checklist of *Heterometrus* Ehrenberg, 1828 with distribution (modified from Prendini & Loria, 2020)

Heterometrus Ehrenberg, 1828

Type species: *Buthus spinifer* Ehrenberg, 1828 (= *Heterometrus spinifer* (Ehrenberg, 1828)).

Heterometrus cimrmani Kovařík, 2004, **stat. rev.** [**Thailand**]

Heterometrus glaucus (Thorell, 1876) [**India** (Nicobar Islands) and **Indonesia** (islands of Bari, Batu, Mentawai, Nias, Siberut, and Sumatra)]

Heterometrus laoticus Couzijn, 1981 [**Laos** and **Thailand**]

Heterometrus longimanus (Herbst, 1800) [**India** (Andaman Islands), **Indonesia** (islands of Bangka, Bengkalis, Borneo, Java, Miang Besar, Riau, and Sumatra), **Malaysia** (mainland), **Singapore** (Ubin Islands) and **Philippines** (islands of Balabac, Luzon, Mindanao, Palawan, and Panay, and Sulu Archipelago)]

Heterometrus minotaurus Plíšková et al., 2016, **stat. rev.** [**Thailand**]

Heterometrus petersii (Thorell, 1876) [**Singapore** (mainland) and **Malaysia** (Penang Islands)]

Heterometrus silenus (Simon, 1884) [**Cambodia**, **Vietnam** (including Phu Quoc Islands) and **Thailand** (including Chang Islands)]

Heterometrus spinifer (Ehrenberg, 1828) [**Malaysia** (including Tioman Islands) and **Thailand**]

Heterometrus thorellii (Pocock, 1892) [**Myanmar**]

Heterometrus laevigatus (Thorell, 1876), *nomen dubium* ["Melbourne, Australia"]